

TABLE 1 - MELTING POINT, ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	M.P. (°C)	% Metal		% Nitrogen		Δ mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.						
[CoL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	178	13.55	14.05	6.35	6.69	9.00	5.1	1620	1310	510	350
[CoL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	191	13.51	14.05	6.62	6.69	8.50	4.9	1620	1315	510	250
[CoL ₂ Q ₂]	186	12.02	12.27	5.63	5.70	12.00	5.0	1610	1310	510	340
[CoL ₂ (DMA) ₂]	167	17.97	18.23	8.26	8.62	8.0	5.1	1610	1305	505	345
[CuL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	212	13.63	15.04	6.17	6.60	10.00	1.8	1615	1310	515	340
[CuL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	201	13.58	15.04	6.52	6.60	9.5	1.7	1620	1310	510	350
[CuL ₂ Q ₂]	179	12.71	12.86	5.48	5.64	8.0	1.75	1625	1320	510	350
[CuL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	226*	16.12	16.02	7.01	7.29	12.0	1.8	1610	1310	515	345
[ZnL ₂ (α -pic) ₂]	249*	15.55	15.37	6.29	6.58	8.5	—	1620	1315	515	340
[ZnL ₂ (γ -pic) ₂]	259*	14.86	15.37	6.50	6.58	9.0	—	1615	1310	505	350
[ZnL ₂ Q ₂]	235	13.37	13.14	5.56	5.62	10.0	—	1625	1305	510	340
[ZnL ₂ (DEA) ₂]	286*	17.12	19.96	7.08	7.26	10.5	—	1620	1320	510	345

* decomposition

 α -pic = α -picoline, γ -pic = γ -picoline, Q = quinoline, DMA = dimethylamine, DEA = diethylamine

atoms have been provided by the occurrence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 510 cm⁻¹ and 350 cm⁻¹ respectively.

In the visible electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes two absorption bands appear ~18.0(30) and ~8.5(20) k.K. region attributable¹⁰ to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(F) transition respectively. Position of absorption bands, molar absorptivity values and magnetic moment suggest a high spin octahedral configuration for the Co(II) complexes. Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band ~15.0(40) k.K. region indicating probably a distorted octahedral configuration, but μ_{eff} values found for Cu(II) complexes are low for Oh symmetry. Although, three transitions are expected for such complexes due to Jahn Teller distortion, often these transitions are observed in the form of a broad envelope, as these are very close in energy. Zinc(II) complexes are presumably octahedral on the basis of analysis, conductance and I. R. spectral data.

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Studies on Complex Compounds of Nickel(II), Palladium(II) and Copper(II) with Benzaldehyde Semicarbazone

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THE present paper reports three complexes, namely, *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Ni(II), *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Pd(II) and *bis*-benzaldehyde semicarbazone Cu(II) of the formulae, M(C₆H₅ON₃)₂ where M = Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II).

Materials :

Semicarbazide hydrochloride (B. D. H. Grade), NiSO₄.6H₂O(S.M.), CuSO₄.5H₂O(E.M.) and PdCl₂ (A.M.) were used.

Complexes :

50 cc of 1% Ni(II) solution were treated with a slight excess of 0.1% hot aqueous ligand on water bath. Immediately after that, 4 (N) NH₄OH was added dropwise until the complex started to be formed. Cu(II)-complex was prepared by similar method. To 30 cc of 1% Pd(II) solution in (1:1) HCl, few cc of conc. sodium acetate solution were added and then treated in cold with a slight excess of 0.1% ligand solution in 50% acetone followed by gradual addition of 4 (N) NH₄OH solution. The complexes were washed with hot water containing a little NH₄OH solution and dried over fused CaCl₂.

Results and Discussions

The results on elemental analysis, ir, uv and magnetic measurements were reported in Table 1.

appeared with centres at 345 cm⁻¹, 335 cm⁻¹ and 410 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes were assigned to ν(Ni-O), ν(Pd-O) and ν(Cu-O) respectively. ν(Cu-O) at 430 cm⁻¹ in *bis*-semicarbazide Cu(II) was already reported by the author⁶. Agamer⁷ assigned ν(M-O) at 325-35 cm⁻¹.

U.V. Spectra :

The principal band observed at 480 mμ due to 1A_{1g}→1B_{1g} transition in Ni(II)-complex was supported by Dhadke *et al*⁸. In Pd(II) complex, band at 420-10 was assigned due to 1A_{1g}→1B_{1g} transition. These facts suggested the square planar geometry of Ni(II) and Pd(II) complexes. Detailed interpretation of square planar complex of Cu(II) seemed complicated. However, 440-380 mμ band was assigned to 2B_{1g}→2E_g transition⁶.

Magnetic Measurement :

Magnetic moment measurement showed Ni(II) and Pd(II) complexes to be diamagnetic. The square planar structures involved dsp² hybridisation. μ_{eff} for

TABLE 1

Complexes	Colours	%M Found (Cal.)	%C Found (Cal.)	%H Found (Cal.)	%N Found (Cal.)	μ _{eff} B.M.	IR spectra, cm ⁻¹			uv spectra λ _{max} , mμ	
							ν(C=N)	ν(C-O)	ν(M-O)		
Ni(C ₈ H ₈ ON ₂) ₂	Green yellow or red	14.78	50.10	4.15	21.94	0	1435 vw	1000 b	345 b	515 b	480
		14.78	50.16	4.18	29.94						
Pd(C ₈ H ₈ ON ₂) ₂	Orange red	24.58	44.40	3.71	19.40	0	1430 vs	1010 s	335 w	515 vw	420-10
		24.58	44.40	3.72	19.42						
Cu(C ₈ H ₈ ON ₂) ₂	Green blue	15.15	49.52	4.10	21.64	1.91	1450 vs	1000 vs	410	610 ms	440-38
		15.16	49.53	4.12	21.67						

Infra Red Spectra :

I.R. spectra of the ligand and complexes were studied in nujol phase between 200 to 4000 cm⁻¹ wave number. The bands at 1570-90 cm⁻¹ and 1400-50 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligand due to C=N and OH₂ bending of enolic form of ligand decreased and modified, their intensities at 1435 and 1420 cm⁻¹, 1430 and 1415 cm⁻¹ and 1450 and 1465 cm⁻¹ respectively in nickel-palladium and copper-complexes showing thus coordination to metal through N of C=N and also the replacement of H of enolic OH. The fact is in conformity with the observation of Saha and Bhattacharyya¹. Rastogi and Saxena² reported the band due to C=N in anils at 1590-1620 cm⁻¹, while Patel and others³ observed it at 1590-1615 cm⁻¹. The bands around 1000 cm⁻¹ due to C-O as marked in the spectra of ligand and complexes, were also supported by Goel and Gupta⁴. Moreover, new bands with centres at 515 cm⁻¹, 510 cm⁻¹ and 610 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes may be attributed to ν(Ni-N), ν(Pd-N) and ν(Cu-N) respectively. Mishra and others⁵ reported bands at 500 and 510 cm⁻¹ due to ν(Ni-N) and ν(Cu-N) vibrations. The bands which

Cu(II)-complex was found to be 1.91 B.M, which was greater than 1.732 B.M. This suggested it to be paramagnetic. A slight greater value was attributed due to orbital contribution and distortion of octahedral structure leading to a square planar structure.

Structures of Benzaldehyde semicarbazone complexes :

The system -CH=N¹-NH²-CO³-NH₂⁴ of the ligand satisfied the condition of formation of chelates. Thus Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II)-chelates can be assigned the tentative structure as follows :

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**Polynuclear Photographic Sensitising Dyes
Derived from 4,4'-p-Phenylene
Bis-(2-Methyl Thiazole), Part-II.**

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In the present investigation a number of symmetrical non-ionic tetranuclear dyes (I) with two central quaternary thiazole residues, two ketomethylene residues and two (=CH-CH=)_n chains derived from the diquaternary salt of 4,4'-p-phenylene bis-(2-methyl thiazole) have been prepared. The variable acidic

nuclei were derived from various ketomethylene compounds like 2-phenyl oxazolone, 2-benzylthio-thiazolone, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone, N,N-diphenyl-thio-barbituric acid and N-phenyl rhodanine.

(I) (A = Variable Acidic nuclei n=1, 2)

The absorption maxima of these dyes were measured. The vinylenic shift for these tetranuclear dyes has been found to be between 75 nm to 92 nm by comparing the absorption maxima data of the tetranuclear dyes (I, n=1) with their higher vinylenic homologues (I, n=2). The vinylenic shifts vary with the nature of the variable nuclei used for the preparation of these dyes.

Experimental

4,4'-p-Phenylene-bis-(2-methyl thiazole) methiodide has been prepared from 1,4-diacetyl benzene¹.

Symmetrical non-ionic tetranuclear dyes (Compound No. 1)

4-Ethoxymethylene-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone² (0.46g) and 4,4'-p-phenylene-bis-(2-methyl thiazole) methiodide (0.8g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine (2-drops) for 10 minutes. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The desired product separated on cooling was recrystallised from absolute ethanol. m.p.-192° (decomp); yield. 30% (Found C, 67.85; H, 4.58; N, 12.51; S, 9.49%. C₃₈H₃₈N₆O₂S₂ requires C, 68.26; H, 4.64; N, 12.57; S, 9.58%).

TABLE 1—TETRANUCLEAR DYES DERIVED FROM 4,4'-p-PHENYLENE-BIS-(2-METHYLTHIAZOLE)

(Structure—I)

Sl. No.	Nature of acidic nucleus 'A'	Value of 'n'	M. P. °C	Yield %	Abs. Max in nm.	Sulphur %		Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	1-methyl-3-phenyl pyrazolone	1	192 (d)	30	483	9.49	9.58	12.51	12.57
2.	-do-	2	206 (d)	25	575	8.78	8.89	11.53	11.67
3.	N-phenyl rhodanine	1	220	25	515	25.03	26.01	7.17	7.58
4.	-do-	2	206 (d)	15	606	24.50	24.61	6.84	7.18
5.	N, N-diphenyl thiobarbituric acid	1	>206	20	475	13.05	14.04	8.81	9.21
6.	-d-	2	247 (d)	25	560	13.17	13.27	8.39	8.71
7.	2-benzyl thiothiazolone	1	173 (d)	15	496	24.05	25.07	6.89	7.31
8.	2-phenyl oxazolone	1	>250	15	523	9.83	9.97	8.43	8.72